

ALISHER NAVOI IN HIS WORKS REASONING OF SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

This In the article, Science is enlightenment a person in spirituality held instead of Alisher Navoi in his works to science hung attention Hazrat Navoi's whole Khurasan across young people education added contribution about word is conducted.

АЛИШЕР НАВОИ В СВОИХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ «РАССУЖДЕНИЯ НАУКИ»

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ABSTRACT

В статье «Наука есть просвещение человека в духовности» вместо Алишера Навои в своих трудах науке уделено внимание всему Хорасану Хазрата Навои, среди молодежи проведен дополнительный вклад в образование слова.

He said: Hey Man, these are the things their names telling he said. To them that's it of things their names telling gave during. Me for you the heavens and the earth absent i know and you guys he didn't cover it - he covered it I also know things " I didn't say that, " he said of a person from the angels superiority side manifestation it has been. Even if he is knowledge. Man land on the face corruption to do, blood it can also be poured, a blessing divine to be science own in place using from the angels superior it can be. Quran From Karim given this verse science is about In it first angels from man before to the ground wants to get off when it was Allah may Allah bless him and grant him peace people knowledge is enlightening that it was for to the ground lowers. Man breed from the angels superiority side science is counted. Scientific of people people between it is also the reason for its glorification that's why

Human all is body and from the soul consists of Man mother that's it two element between lives for the body the most need health, whole clothes, good food If so, the soul for the most necessary this spiritual maturity. Spiritual to perfection a person, first of all, his own faith, science and craft with are enough Ruhan pure, meaning mature person people interest own

benefit superior put one step to the height achieves Encyclopedia knowledge the owner has been Hazrat Alisher Navoi in his works, knowledge is a craft, to enlightenment separately attention is directed. This is Navoi's a lot in his works manifestation will be Among them, his,, Farhad and Shirin" of the Chin people mind the prince to be Farhad's divine love is glorified. The main character in it love with was born and this love every one of them in practice it seems was Navoi Farhad perfect a person as to the student introduces and his perfection science is a craft has been love with connects

Craft asrabon netkum the end

Take it mud I'm leaving the end

He says Navoi real of science his power a person with closely dependence about,, Farhad and Shirin" in the epic. Farhad in the work his own from his teachers learned science, craft to his heart goes, he is one of the coaches received knowledge to his heart so love with it is absorbed in it special one divine to power becomes Alisher Navoi science to learn aspiration of a person to perfection to achieve the most higher he knows the way, that 's right skill, experience and knowledge the owner has been a person out of ignorance nari, from mischief long will be says and this own also mentioned in his works passes. love with was born Farhad to grow up and mature deliver so much sad, indifferent being remains. His father in the child sadness take away for to him science secrets, craft to teach ok sees science in his son sadness leaving the most main he knows as a tool.

Ato after seeing this type love due to

Appropriate realized science quote

Teachers by given science sincerity with learned Farhad that's it science to blood absorbs and to him always action to do strives Farhad books so many diligent with reads one opened to the sheet again look does not put, all to his heart give birth listening takes

If one layer saw every lesson,

Open again no erdi ul sheet.

What do you mean? arrow to pass motto,

Mold in mind step by step go

Seeing true love infatuation saying

Find it confused sad heart still

Each of the problem the solution full science, high perception with pressing transition can In this place Imam al- Bukhari the following thoughts are also science Allah by given higher a blessing that confirms,, In the world from science another salvation no and ever may not be ".

Today's globalized in time which one developed to the state don't look at it science, technology ahead will be If in the country to knowledge attention strong if so, to young people deep potential knowledge if given that's it state always will increase. Alisher Navoi is also his own period to young people from the hand came all help gave His from his students has been Ghiyaziddin Khondamir in his work " Makorim ul- akhlaq ". Navoi's to students material help that his students showed never how without difficulties science is a craft learning for chance by creating that he gave note is enough and Hazrat Navoi led by of Khorasan different in the regions science dargahs and madrasahs are also built that he did writing passes. " Ikhlosiya ", " Khalosiya ", " Shifaiya ", " Nizomiya ", " Khusravia " madrasa and roommates these are including

In these places of the time the most famous scientists different from the sciences a lesson giving young people science light with enjoy reached

Poet science owners has been scientists, trainers appreciates Theirs giving education to the treasury compares, one letter taught of a scientist service Ganga equals

Right on the way who to you one letter have taught hurt with

Spin perfect, aning about face gang with

But Navoi science take to him action did not scientists condemns them wicked is called a scientist. Poet in his "Mahbub ul- qulub " work own from science right useful does not receive, reads, teaches, but himself action He calls the "knowledgeable" who do not, "wise ".

I am a scientist reached sorry

Oh Ghaniykim, Maliga buhl reached place

They died face desire is a dream this

Elga it has been from work attention

„ Science to learn religious piety for, no the world society for. Goodbye genius - without rain sir and invalid scholar - dobbaki to the upload book emphasizes a poet in his "Mahbub ul- qulub " work.

Hazrat Alisher Navoi of science Do n't spread your qualities light up will give. Science is enlightenment of a person to maturity the only deliverer of salvation that different evidence with explaining will give.„ Science of a person his heart one to the world turn it into one to the drop whole one the river hides in his words full meaning ; talk mysterious to decorations wrapping I know that he speaks Allah by given a gift that in the epic " Hayrat ul- Abrar ". writing passes. Writer's is also artistic works with one in line to science about manuscripts to us heritage leaves His to linguistics („ Muhakamat ul- lug'atayn ") history („ Tarikhi angel and hukamo ", „ History property ajam ") fiqh („ Siraj ul- Muslim "), Aruz related to science (Mezon ul- avzon). one how much works today's of the day that's it period from history, culture speaker main sources is considered This is us scientific works through that's it time Wake up period of the development of science where level development that he found knowing we get can Navoi's scientific in the subject He is also a reader of his works for clear example and collections rich in samples is considered To linguistics about books through today's day young people Uzbek language lexicon, etymology that's it at the time development learning with present of the day information to compare opportunity have we will be Navoi injections through while our literature in history the poet is a scholar to his life about of knowledge informed we will be

Navoi mother so encyclopedia knowledge the owner was, his creativity science to the sea like, wanted a diver from the sea to himself necessary the turds take and his from Ziya enjoy to be possible Science the most virtuous is action. Because a person science and craft and enlightenment with in life own instead of have will be Man right to the road did not put it to goodness did not lead or some kind of bias has been science science not to say need People interest looking forward to his life relief person who enters spirituality enriching science real is science. Mankind learned if never when less it won't be. About it Quran It is also mentioned in Karim :„ Allah from you faith brought by science ato done breeds to (high) ranks (ranks). raise ". Really knowledgeable a person chorus It won't be own on work, knowledge right uses

and will increase. Jonahon We are also young people in Uzbekistan science to get all conditions enough Of them fruitful using science to the rays have to be our the most higher is our duty.

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